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Green Accounting Disclosure And Financial Performance Of Oil And Gas Companies In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The upward trend in oil spillage in Nigeria, especially in the oil producing areas, has heightened the the agitation for green accounting disclosures. This paper studied of green accounting and financial performance of oil and gas companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group. The variables of the study include; green accounting disclosure (proxied by environmental cost), return on assets (ROA), net profit margin (NPM) and return on capital employed (ROCE). Data obtained were analysed using descriptive statistics which include the mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum values; and inferential using correlation and granger causality estimation tool. The findings showed that green accounting disclosure has no significant relationship net profit margin and return on capital employed. Although a weak, positive and significant relationship exists between GAD and ROA, the granger causality test revealed that there is no causal relationship between GAD and financial performance (ROA, NPM and ROCE) variables. It was however recommended that oil and gas companies should despise the negative insignificant relationship exhibited by green accounting disclosure and maintain the culture of disclosing their environmental cost and green projects in their annual statement for the pleasure of stakeholders to make informed decision.

Keywords: Green accounting disclosure, Return on Asset, Net Profit Margin Return on capital employed

INTRODUCTION

In the current millennial generation, Nigeria certainly has been caught up with the rapid advances in technological development and able to compete globally, and the modern economy is becoming increasingly sophisticated, which can lead to various problems related to environmental degradation. The environmental damage caused by oil and gas activities is beginning to draw attention to society. The activities planned to be carried out by the company cannot be separated from the surrounding community (Agustia, 2021). Considering, the importance of the development of a modern economy like today, various issues related to the environment such as global warming, eco-efficiency and other industrial activities that have a direct impact on the surroundings exist. As corporate activities have a greater impact on environmental issues and nature conservation, the accounting field plays a role in environmental conservation efforts through voluntary disclosure in financial reports about environmental costs (Panggabean and Deviarti, 2022). This case indicates the need for the implementation of green accounting.

Green accounting is a type of accounting that attempts to factor environmental costs into the financial results of operations. It has been argued that gross domestic product ignores the environment and therefore decision makers need a revised model that incorporates green accounting. Environmental pollution is one of the problems facing the world today, due to its impact on society, nature and performance (Khan & Ghouri, 2011). The phenomenon of environmental pollution cause by oil and gas

exploration, has received increasing attention in recent times, especially in light of the industrial progress in the contemporary world and the diversity of sources of pollution, and the attempt of industrial companies, particularly oil and gas firms to get rid of its waste is harmful to the environment and people (Chinwe, 2013).

As a result of the development of interest in environmental performance as one of the foundations of development in any country, non-use of modern scientific methods that analyse environmental costs and provide detailed information on those costs and the efforts and amounts that companies bear for the purpose of environmental protection will give guaranteed results on the extent of their success or failure (Nas, 2016). Therefore, new concepts of accounting emerged, such as green accounting, and the names have multiplied across stages of concern for the environment (accounting for a sustainable environment, environmental accounting, environmental impact accounting, social responsibility accounting, etc.), and then the concept of green accounting emerged when it was considered the subject of the system (Moorthy & Yacob, 2013).

According to Malik & Mittal (2015), Green accounting is important for developing economies, this is because green accounting helps in saving environmental and development problems. Environmental accounting will help countries in addressing the economic problems associated with climate change. The World Bank asserts that the world losses a significant amount of money due to environmental changes. Green accounting would help in solving environmental changes leading to improved performance for companies and firms operating in developing countries. Firms that have adopted green accounting have led to reduced operational costs during environmental changes.

Statement of the Problem

Green accounting reports remains voluntary. However, the unprecedented level and increase of oil spillage has escalated the demand for environmental accounting disclosures in Nigeria, which are majorly caused by corrosion of pipeline, which amounts to 50% of the total spillages in Nigeria (Library.thinkingquest.org, 2010) sabotage, vandalism, oil production operation, ship seepage, tankers and oil terminal leakages, equipment failure or malfunction, deliberate/incidental discharge of oil from leaking tankers and ships etc. The different types of oil spillages and gas flaring by the oil and gas companies in Nigeria, impacts negatively on the environment and the inhabitants of the host communities suffer. The effect of oil spillages depends on the enormity of the spillage, what is affected in the environment and the season it occurred (Environmental Pollution Center, 2018). The leakage of such oil also catalyzes a number of difficult health problems such as respiratory difficulties, skin rashes, cancer, gastrointestinal disorders and malnutrition.

The disclosure of a firm's green costs is thought to make the firm more responsive (Cortez & Cudia, 2011; Muller, *et al.*, 2011; Shelly, *et al.*, 2007), and it is also a key determinant of profitability and performance (Cortez & Cudia, 2011; Muller, *et al.*, 2011; Shelly, Fust & Lisa, 2007). (Okoye & Ezejiofor, 2013; Lee, *et al.*, 2011). In Nigeria, however, only a small number of recent research have found a link between green accounting and profitability (Agbiogwu, *et al.*, 2016; Nnamani, *et al.*, 2017). There have also been studies that show that green accounting has a detrimental impact on a company's profitability, (Adekanmi, *et al.*, 2015; Makori & Jagongo, 2013). As the environment is continuously deteriorating as a result of increased industrial activity, environmental green accounting is increasingly being called for in the organization to keep track of the environmental activities to know whether the generated data has significant impact on the performance of companies, particularly the petroleum and gas companies (Oti & Mbu-Ogar, 2018). It is on this context that this study attempt to examine the green accounting disclosure and financial performance of oil and gas companies in Nigeria.

The study specific objectives include the following.

1. Green accounting disclosure and return on assets of oil and gas companies in Nigeria.
2. Green accounting disclosure and net profit margin of oil and gas companies in Nigeria.
3. Green accounting disclosure and return on capital employed in Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Green or environmental accounting is a term with a variety of meanings. In many contexts, green accounting is taken to mean the identification and reporting of environment specific costs (Nkwoji, 2021). Green accounting is a method of measuring, in economic terms, the performance of any type of organization in relation to the environment. The goal is to provide information about the company's operational performance based on environmental protection. Conventional accounting only provides economic information that is financial in nature to shareholders and bondholders for decision making. Performance measures need to be increased to improve existing performance measures. Environmental impacts need to be reported as a manifestation of responsibility towards stakeholders (Astuti, 2012). Green accounting or environmental accounting aims at achieving sustainable development, maintaining a favorable relationship with the community, and pursuing effective and efficient environmental conservation activities. The accounting procedures allow a company to identify the cost of environmental conservation during the normal course of business, identify benefit gained from such activities, and provide the best possible means of quantitative measurement, in monetary value or physical units, and support the communication of its results.

Green accounting is a method of reporting the impact that a company's management activities have on the environment by including it in financial reports. Ningsih and Rachmawati (2021) Green Accounting aims to link the environmental budget and business operating funds. Green accounting also provides opportunities to reduce energy and natural resources, reduce health risks, and promote competitive advantage for companies. In this way, green accounting is an effort to improve the economics of a company without ignoring the state of the surrounding environment. It is accounting for any costs and benefits that arise from change to a firm's, products and processes where the change also involves a change in environmental impact.

Green accounting is a relatively new concept which aims to include in the traditional measurement of economic development the cost for using the environment as inputs to production and as a sink for wastes. From the point of view of green accounting, land, water, and other natural resources are treated as inputs and assets in the production of goods and services of an entity (Virola, De Perio & Angeles, 2000). Green accounting or environmental accounting is the practice of incorporating principles of environmental management and conservation into reporting practices and cost/benefit analyses (Rewadikar, 2014). Environmental accounting allows a business to see the impact of economically sustainable practices in everything. It allows accountants to report on the economic impact of those decisions to stakeholders so as to allow for proactive decision making about processes that simultaneously meet environmental regulations while adding to the bottom line.

Green accounting according to Lewis and Chopparapu (2017), mainly focuses on the role in which an enterprise has toward the environment. Environmental change has a bearing change in not only the environment but also in the economy. A suitable environment has a positive impact on the business sector by creating an appropriate environment for enterprising (Hecht, 2012). Green accounting examines how the environment affects the financial accounting system in terms of costs and benefits. It is an approach to measure and communicate information related to environmental activities of economic units with environmental impact to the parties concerned and society in a manner that enables control and evaluation of their environmental performance (Moorthy & Yacob, 2013). Green accounting has led to sustainable development by creating a peaceful environment for the enterprise (Gray & Laughlin, 2012).

Categories of Environmental Accounting

Green accounting involves estimation of environmental expenditures/cost, capitalization of those environmental expenditures, identification of environmental liabilities and measurement of environmental liabilities. There are several forms of green or environmental accounting including:

Green management accounting: Green or environmental management accounting is the identification, prioritization, quantification or qualification, and incorporation of environmental costs into business decisions (Astuti, 2012). Green management accounting uses data about environmental costs and performance for business decisions. It collects cost, production, inventory, and waste cost and

performance for business decisions. Environmental management accounting thus represents a combined approach which provides for the transition of data from financial accounting and cost accounting to increase material efficiency, reduce environmental impact and risk, and reduce costs of environmental protection.

Green or environmental cost accounting: The environmental cost accounting deals with environmental costs in order to reach the full cost accounting, i.e. the identification, evaluation, and allocation of conventional costs, environmental costs, and social costs to processes, products, activities, or budgets. In some organizations, accountants are held responsible to identify and track green costs often times working with site, research and development, and production managers when planning their budgets. In the past, such costs were buried in overhead preventing a clear picture of the cost savings and benefits to the product, process, system or facility responsible for the green initiatives. Green accounting help management recognize that the tax benefits, rebates and lower costs of being environmentally friendly add up to a real bottom-line reward for doing the right thing (Eilola, 2017).

Environmental financial accounting: Environmental cost accounting, environmental management accounting, ecological accounting and natural resource accounting. Environmental financial accounting aims to the true disclosure in financial statements in the end of period. That is including environmental dimension in the published sheets of operations. Environmental expenditures/costs: These are expenses or costs related to environmental measures including production-related costs and product research and development expenditures which are incurred primarily for ensuring protection of environment. Total environmental expenditures can be classified into six categories such as capital investment, operating costs, research and development cost, environment administration and planning, expenditures for remedial measures and recovery measures (Eze, 2021).

Ecological accounting: Ecological cost accounting is used to refer to the preparation of accounts according to physical data only. In this respect, ecological accounting is mainly used to prepare an asset management plans at local administration level. Such plans provide a tool to evaluate the condition and life cycle of any particular physical asset.

Natural resource accounting: Natural resource accounting is called after inclusion of environmental aspects into the system of national accounts. Emphasis is given to natural assets, deterioration in its quality in order to get an environmentally adjusted economic indicator such as environmental gross national income (Rewadikar, 2014).

Financial performance

Financial performance in business is an account of income and expenditure by the management to the shareholders. This entails calculating a company's or business's profitability, market worth, and growth prospects. Financial performance is needed for a company to find out and to evaluate the level of success of a company based on financial activities that have been implemented (Rudianto, 2013). Financial performance is a subjective measure of how well a firm can use assets from its primary mode of business and generate revenues. It shows the general well-being of a firm and its true financial position (Eze, 2021). Financial performance can be looked at, as the level of performance of an organization at a point in time. This could be measured in terms of overall profits and losses or asset utilization. Likewise, a company's financial performance is determined by social performance and accounting data, such as previous audited financial records (Magara, Aminga, & Momanyi, 2015). Financial performance is the outcome or accomplishment that has been accomplished by the administration of an organization in overseeing organization resources viably during a specific period. It is a description of a company's financial state through time, including both elements of fund raising and fund channeling, and is commonly quantified using capital adequacy, liquidity, and profitability metrics.

According to Iliemena and Okolocha (2019) the measures of financial performance of an organization are as varied as the motive for the measurement. Organisational financial performance is measured to give the account of stewardship by the management team to the shareholders. The key aspect of this involves measuring the profitability, return on asset, net profit margin, return on capital employed and growth prospect of a company. The measurement of the effect of environmental accounting on performance

examines the nature of the relationship between some indicator of environmental reporting or performance with the company's financial performance obtained from the accounting information such as the historical audited financial statements of the respective companies. Financial performance is commonly used as an indicator of a firm's financial health over a given period of time. In this study, financial performance is measured return on asset, net profit margin and return on capital employed.

Returns on assets

As one of the traditional accounting and profitability measures employed to measure financial performance, return on assets shows whether a company is able to generate an adequate return on the assets employed. In a study on green accounting disclosure and financial performance of oil and gas companies in Nigeria by Ezeagba et al (2017), it was revealed that there is a significant relationship between green accounting disclosure and return on assets.

Net Profit Margin

The net profit margin is defined as the profit or net income obtained as a percentage of the revenue generated. It is obtained by dividing profits by revenues of a business or company. The net profit margin is generally represented as a percentage, and it may also be expressed in the decimal format. The net profit margin shows how much of the money recorded in the form of revenues is translating to profits. The net income is sometimes referred to as the bottom line of an organisation or the net profit. Net margin is the other name of the net profit margin. Net profits and net income recorded in the income statements can be used interchangeably as they point to the same thing.

Theoretical Review

Stakeholder Theory

Freeman came up with the stakeholder theory (1984). According to the hypothesis, organizations disclose environmental information as a result of stakeholder pressure, and that an organization would respond to the worries and expectations of influential stakeholders, with some reactions taking the form of strategic disclosures. The society, shareholders, creditors, workers, customers, and suppliers, all of whom may be interested in the business's social and environmental actions, are stakeholders in the context of a business. These individuals are referred to as stakeholders by Freeman (1984). Stakeholders vary in terms of their type and extent of influence on a company's operations. Organizations are thus responsible to these stakeholders and rely on their continual approval to sustain a successful operating environment, according to Roberts (1992). Stakeholder theory focuses on establishing elements that influence a company's ability to continue to exist. According to stakeholder theory, companies require the support and acknowledgment of stakeholders in order to improve their environmental performance. These enterprises must communicate their positions, efforts, and accomplishments in the application of environmental responsibility to their stakeholders (Elijido-Ten, 2004). Firms must consequently increase stakeholder trust, remove misunderstandings about environmental protection, and build relationships with external stakeholders, before disclosing additional environmental data.

Empirical Review

Omoniyi (2022) investigated how green accounting affects the financial performance of Oando Plc. The variables of the study include; environmental cost, net income, return on assets (ROA), return on capital employed (ROCE), where Leverage and firm size are used as control variables. Data obtained were analysed using descriptive statistics which include the mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum values; and inferential using correlation and granger causality. The findings revealed that there is no relationship between environmental cost and net income and return on capital employed. It is however recommended that Oando Plc should overlook the insignificant effect of green accounting disclosure and cultivate the habit to disclosing the environmentally event and activities in their annual report as this will be of great use for some stakeholders.

Nwafor et al. (2021) examined the effect of green accounting on the financial performance of oil and gas companies 2010-2020. A quantitative technique was adopted and Ex post facto research design was employed for the study. Data were obtained from annual reports and accounts of the companies for the

periods 2010 to 2020. The hypotheses were tested using regression analysis with aid of e-view 9.0. The results showed that environmental cost accounting has a significant effect on the financial performance of oil and gas companies. Also, the study found that green management accounting has significant effect on the financial performance of oil and gas firms.

Ojo and Balogun (2019) environmental accounting disclosure and profitability of selected firms quoted on the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE). The data for the study were collected from annual reports and accounts of eighteen (18) randomly selected quoted companies in Nigerian Stock Exchange. The data were analyzed using multiple regression models. The key finding of the study shows that there is significant negative relationship between Environmental Accounting Disclosure and Return on Capital employed (ROCE), Earnings per Share (EPS) and a significant positive relationship and Net Profit Margin (NPM) and Dividend per Share (DPS). Based on this it was recommended that government should enforce compliance of environmental accounting disclosure in the company's annual reports and accounts. In addition, government should give tax credit to companies that have been complying with its environmental laws and that environmental disclosure should be made compulsory in Nigeria so as to improve the performance of companies and create sustainable environment for conducive living.

The study by Nwaiwu and Oluka (2018) focused on environmental cost disclosure and oil and gas financial performance in Nigeria. The impact of environmental cost disclosure and financial performance indicators on listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria is investigated in this study. Time series data were acquired from the Central Bank of Nigeria's annual financial reporting and economic review; Pearson product moment coefficient of correlation and multiple linear regression analysis were performed using SPSS version 22. The econometric findings looked at whether proper information on environmental costs and corporate environmental rules have a positive significant influence on financial performance metrics.

As a result, the research advocated for regulatory enforcement to ensure sufficient environmental cost disclosure and reporting. Management of Nigerian oil and gas businesses should build a well articulated environmental cost system to provide a conflict-free corporate environment conducive to better corporate performance.

Ezeagba et al. (2017) examined the relationship between environmental accounting disclosures and return on equity of food and beverage companies in Nigeria. It also examined the relationship between environmental accounting disclosures and return on capital employed of food and beverage companies in Nigeria, among others. Four hypotheses were formulated and tested in line with the objectives of the study. Data for the study were collected through secondary sources and analyzed using Pearson's correlation statistical technique and multiple regression, with the aid of SPSS version 20.00. The study revealed that there is a significant relationship between environmental accounting disclosures and return on equity of selected companies. It also revealed a negative relationship between environmental accounting disclosures and return on capital employed and net profit margin of selected companies. Based on these findings, the researcher recommends among others, that firms should adopt uniform reporting and disclosure standards of environmental practices. This will enhance control and measurement of performance. The study also advocates that firms (especially smaller ones), should be encouraged to disclose their environmental practices in their annual reports.

Nnamani et al. (2017) have assessed the financial performance of the list of Nigerian manufacturers as being affected by sustainable accounting. These companies belonged to the sub-sector of brewery. The secondary details were derived from the annual reports and accounts for the total asset, equity revenue, total personal turnover and return on assets of the three breweries listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange, and were examined by utilizing the commonly less square method of estimate. This study showed that the reporting of sustainability has a favorable and important impact on the financial performance of the breweries under scrutiny.

METHODOLOGY

The research design employed in this study is the ex-post facto research design, in order to establish a relationship between green accounting and financial performance of oil and gas companies. This study was treated as ex-post facto research since it relied on historical data. This is appropriate because ex-post

facto research aims at measuring and establishing the relationship between one variable and another or the effect of one variable on another, in which the variables involved are not manipulated by the researcher (Kothari & Garg, 2014). The population of this study consists of the eleven (11) oil and gas companies listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange as at 31st December, 2023. They include; Japaul Oil & Maritime Services Plc, Oando Plc, Beco Petroleum Products Plc, Capital Oil Plc, Conoil Plc, Rak Unity Petroleum Plc, Eterna Plc, Forte Oil Plc, Mobil Oil Plc, MRS Oil Nigeria Plc and Total Nigeria Plc. A sample of the six (Capital Oil Plc, Conoil Plc, Mobil Oil Plc, Total Nigeria Plc, Forte Oil Plc and Japaul Oil & Maritime Services Plc) oil and gas companies were used. Data were gathered from the published financial statements of the six companies from 2017-2022. The reason for the choice of this time frame is availability of published annual report and accounts of the selected companies. The data analysis for the study took the form of descriptive statistics and inferential statistics. This research work adopted the panel least square (PLS) regression analysis with longitudinal (panel) regression using Stata 12 statistical software. The reason for adopting panel data regression is because of the number of Oil and Gas firms and the period of time involved.

Measurement of Variables

Variable Name	Type of Variable	Symbol	Definition/Proxy
Green Accounting Disclosure	Independent	GAD	This is measure by the total cost incurred on the environmental activities of the company
Return on Assets	Dependent	ROA	Measure as net income divided by the total asset of the company.
Net profit Margin	Dependent	NPM	It is obtained by dividing profits by revenues of a business or company.
Return on Capital Employed	Dependent	ROCE	Measure by earnings before interest and tax divided by capital employed.

Model specification

The model was stated adapting the studies of Agbiogwu, *et al.*, 2016; Jeroh & Okoro 2016; Onyekwelu & Ugwu 2017 and Eniola, 2022) while examining the relationship between environmental cost disclosure and corporate performance. The model is stated thus:

$$ROA = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 GAD_{it} + \alpha_2 NPM_{it} + \alpha_3 ROCE_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots\dots\dots(i)$$

$$NPM = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 GAD_{it} + \alpha_2 ROA_{it} + \alpha_3 ROCE_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots\dots\dots(ii)$$

$$ROCE = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 GAD_{it} + \alpha_2 ROA_{it} + \alpha_3 NPM_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots\dots\dots(iii)$$

Where;

GAD = Green Accounting Disclosure (Proxied by Environmental Cost)

ROA = Return on Asset

NPM = Net profit Margin

ROCE = return on capital employed

ε = Error term

α_0 = Constants; $\alpha_1 \dots \alpha_2$ = coefficient

DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

To know more about the time series behaviour of the data set, the descriptive statistics of the variables were examined and the results are shown respectively in Tables 4.2.

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics

	GAD	ROA	NPM	ROCE
Mean	4030.000	0.552532	6.794321	3.040892
Median	3382.000	0.426221	5.699475	3.181510
Maximum	4242.000	0.688390	2.467100	5.375040
Minimum	3279.000	0.567200	1.930000	2.1928.90
Std. Dev.	364.2387	0.419918	4.234316	3.923881
Skewness	0.541365	-0.035123	0.276778	-0.639777
Kurtosis	1.795438	1.837490	2.341713	2.664162
Jarque-Bera	0.512496	0.433455	1.263766	2.989661
Probability	0.633669	0.296198	0.531590	0.224287
Sum	21100.00	0.923885	2.785672	1.656766
Sum Sq. Dev.	502614.0	0.704221	7.17E+08	2.51E+09

Source: *Eviews Output*

The result of the descriptive analyses of the various series in table 1 shows a considerable level of variability in the behavioral pattern of the series. For green accounting disclosure which is measured by environmental cost, the mean value of 4030 indicates that an average yearly cost on environmental activities is over 4 million naira. The standard deviation of 0.42 of ROA suggests that only minimum data points are lying far away from the mean whereas the mean value of 55% approximately indicates that the total asset contributes to the profitability of the firm. Net profit margin has a mean of 6.79, a median value of 5.70 and a standard deviation of 4.23 indicating that the variable is less volatile. Return on capital employed showed that on average, the capital employed generate 3.0 percent of the employed capital. The standard deviation of 3.92 reveal that majority of the distribution were closed to the mean value. However, the Jacque-Berra statistics being greater than 5% accept the normality test for all the variable series.

Table 2 Correlation Matrix

		GAD	ROA	NPM	ROCE
GAD	Correlation Coefficient	1.000			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.			
ROA	Correlation Coefficient	.345**	1.000		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.		
NPM	Correlation Coefficient	.013	.007	1.000	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.794	.886	.	
ROCE	Correlation Coefficient	-.019	-.013	.696**	1.000
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.707	.788	.000	.000

Table 2 shows the relationship of the dependent and independent variables. The Pearson correlations were run to examine the relationship between green accounting disclosure and financial performance. There was positive and significant correlation between GAD and ROA ($r = .345, p = .001$). Also, the association between GAD and NPM was weak, positive but insignificant ($r = .013, p = .794$). Also, the relationship between GAD and ROCE was weak, negative and insignificant $r = -.019, p = .707$. From the result we deduced that a mixed relationship exists between green accounting disclosure (GAD) and financial performance.

Granger Causality Tests

Table 3 Granger Causality

Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
ROA does not Granger Cause GAD	3	0.05986	0.9420
GAD does not Granger Cause ROA		3.16269	0.0550
NPM does not Granger Cause GAD	3	0.54123	0.5870
GAD does not Granger Cause NPM		3.03553	0.0612
ROCE does not Granger Cause GAD	3	0.62809	0.5397
GAD does not Granger Cause ROCE		1.81746	0.1779

Source: *Author's Computation using Eview's 9*

This study also proceeds to establish the causal relationship between GAD and financial performance of oil and gas companies in Nigeria, using Pairwise Granger Causality Test. The granger causality test result seen in table 3: showed that return on assets does not cause green accounting disclosure; green accounting disclosure does not granger cause return on asset. Furthermore, causality relationship between net profit margin and green accounting disclosure of oil and gas companies in Nigeria shows that, NPM does not cause GAD and GAD does not cause NPM. The result also showed that return on capital employed does not granger cause green accounting disclosure and green accounting disclosure does not granger causes return on capital employed.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The first specific objectives of this paper are to examine the relationship between green accounting disclosure (proxied by environmental cost) and return on asset of oil and gas companies. Finding obtained from analysed data revealed the existence of a weak, positive and significant relationship between GAD and ROA of oil companies. This finding is in agreement with the study of Nwafor et al. (2021) and Ezeagba et al. (2017) who investigated the impact of the environmental expenses on the performance of the selected Nigerian businesses including oil and gas and found that environmental expenses had a favorable impact on a company's performance. On contrary, of Adekanmi, Adedoyin, and Adewole (2015) reported a negative effect socio-environmental accounting of listed companies' financial performance.

Furthermore, this study investigated the correlation between environmental cost and net profit margin of oil and gas companies. Result showed the existence of a weak positive correlation and no causal association between the environmental cost and net profit margin. This result is in disagreement with the findings Ojo and Balogun (2019) who analyzed, using secondary data obtained from 18 randomly selected annual reporting and accounting, the impacts of environmental and social costs on the performance of Nigerian producer companies. Ojo and Balogun (2019) opined those environmental expenses have a a significant positive relationship on Net Profit Margin (NPM) and dividend per share. The finding is however in line with Eniola (2022) who reported insignificant negative relationship between green accounting disclosure and financial performance of Oando plc.

Lastly, this study assesses the association between environmental cost and the Return on Capital Employed (ROCE) of oil and gas companies. Findings showed that the ROCE does not exhibit a Granger causal relationship with the GAD of oil and gas companies. In addition, a negative and insignificant relationship was found between ROCE and GAD. This finding is in agreement with the study of Eniola (2022) and Adekanmi, Adedoyin, and Adewole (2015) whose study considered the factor of socio-environmental accounting of the companies listed in Nigeria and found that socio-environmental performance of socio-environmental reporting by the Nigerian traded businesses showed a substantial negative effect. Nevertheless, this result failed to be in tandem with the study of Ezejiofor, *et al* (2016)

and Oti and Mbu-Ogar (2018) whose findings showed that environmental costs impact the profits generated by companies in Nigeria substantially and favorably.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study estimated Green Accounting Disclosures and Financial Performance. The study examined salient literatures from conceptualization, theoretical and empirical review. The study population comprised all the listed Oil and Gas companies in Nigerian Exchange Group as at 31st December 2022. The sampled of the study was six major oil companies using judgmental sampling techniques. As a result, this study examine the relationship between Green Accounting Disclosures and Financial Performance of the Oil and Gas Companies from 2017 - 2022. The choice of variables used in this study is informed by previous empirical studies on this topic. These variables are green accounting (proxied by environmental cost), ROA, NPM and ROCE. The variables were grouped into dependent variable and independent variables. The secondary data were computed and analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The use of descriptive statistics involves; mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum values. Also, the study used the correlation and granger causality data analysis techniques in testing the listed above variables.

Result from the correlation analysis revealed that a positive and significant correlation exist between ROA and GAD of oil and gas companies within the study period. However, NPM and ROCE were insignificantly correlated with GAD of oil and gas companies in Nigeria. In addition, ROCE was negatively correlated with GAD of oil and gas companies. To further confirm the finding, the granger causality test revealed that there is no relationship between GAD and ROA of oil and gas companies. In addition, there is no causal association between the green accounting disclosure and net profit margin of oil companies and that the ROCE does not exhibit a causal relationship with the GAD of oil companies.

In view of the findings, it was concluded that there is negative but insignificant relationship between green accounting disclosures and financial performance of listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria.

Although, empirical revealed that green accounting disclosure is negatively correlated with financial performance of oil and gas companies in Nigeria, this negative influence is insignificant and considerably low. It is needless to emphasis that, some stakeholders are in dire need of this information to be abreast with the contributions to society of these companies. On this ground, it is recommended that oil and gas companies should despise the insignificant impact exhibited by green accounting disclosure and maintain the culture of disclosing their environmental cost and green projects in their annual statement for the pleasure of stakeholders to make informed decision. Also, oil and gas companies should focus on green accounting project that will sustain the corporation ability, promoting the corporation corporate social responsibility and goodwill and in order to help fulfill short-term financial obligations and other payables and this will in return aid in the enhancement of return on capital employed.

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